

8-Theory on Fermionic & Bosonic Propagations

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Abstract:

By analyzing the nature of variations according to their numeric features, i.e. even for fermions and primes to boson, it is possible to derive their behavior as described by either scalar fields or a vector field. It is also possible to classify those arbitrary variations to real or complex according to the number of variations in the set. Reader is assumed to be familiar with the 8T thesis as little no explanations will be made regarding the equations presented.

Introduction

$$\left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \right] \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \right] \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g' = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^M \delta g_k = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

We partitioned and discretized into a series of arbitrary variations that vanish into matter. We do not have any data regarding the position on the manifold in which those arbitrary variations appear, nor can we assume they possess momenta, as we invoked stationarity on the Lorenzian. M_0 is the connected manifold.

$$M = M_0 \times R \quad (1.12)$$

In other words, arbitrary variations, which vanish into matter, can be regarded and described by scalar fields that are real, since they have an even amount of variations.

$$\sum_{k=1}^M \delta g_k \in \mathbb{R} \quad (1.121)$$

Those arbitrary variations, still a subject to additional variance. Such a variance is either prime or one in our framework. These are the variations associated with bosonic propagation. One associated with the strong and each prime with additional coupling term, weak, electric and so on. Because of their prime number feature, they are not vanishing like a fermion scalar but rather as a vector propagation all across.

The propagation is associated with a variation of the ∇^2 operator to the setting of the stationary manifold. The bosonic ripple field is than described by:

$$\nabla^2 = \frac{\partial^2 M(x)}{\partial^2 g} + \frac{\partial^2 M(y)}{\partial^2 g} + \frac{\partial^2 M(z)}{\partial^2 g} \quad (1.9)$$

In other words, it is a vector field propagating all across the matrix, due to its prime number feature, for the second element in the coupling constant series and above.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (2)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (2.1)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \quad (2.11)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ...$$

$$(1): (30): (128): (850): (9254) ...$$

Since the bosonic propagation is associated with prime amount of variations, we can associate it to a complex field, which than require a Hermitian conjunction in order to perform measurement upon. In other words, we can associate bosonic fields to complex vector fields.

$$N_V = 2V + 1; N_V \in \mathbb{P} \quad (3)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{C}$$

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)